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Thermal behavior and long-term performance of steel slag in housing under future climate conditions

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Abstract: Energy consumption in buildings—particularly due to the use of air conditioning systems—is expected to increase as a result of climate change in Brazil by 2050. In this context, it becomes essential to adopt bioclimatic strategies that enhance the thermal performance of buildings, with a particular focus on social housing. This study aimed to evaluate the applicability of steel slag (SS) as an adaptive construction material, considering its impact on thermal loads and thermal comfort across different Brazilian climate zones. The methodology was based on computational simulations using the EnergyPlus software, with a social housing unit from the “Vila Reciclos” project as a model. This unit employs blocks with SS in its walls. Two building models (one with SS and one conventional reference) were analyzed in nine representative Brazilian cities, under both current climate conditions and future projections (RCP 8.5 scenario). The results showed that the use of SS significantly reduced heating loads, particularly in humid subtropical climates, with improvements of up to 33%. In tropical climates, cooling loads were also reduced, although to a lesser extent. Furthermore, SS contributed to maintaining thermal comfort under future climate scenarios. It is concluded that SS is a viable and sustainable solution to help mitigate the impacts of climate change in social housing.

Keywords: Energy efficiency. Thermal insulation. Climate adaptation. Heat load. Simulation modeling.

1. Introduction

Energy consumption in buildings is responsible for a considerable portion of global energy demand, with air conditioning being a primary contributing factor (González Torres et al., 2022). To address this issue, bioclimatic strategies have been a subject of extensive investigation, as they facilitate the optimization of thermal performance through the judicious selection of materials and environmental conditions (Elaouzy & El Fadar, 2022a; Manzano et al., 2015).

In Brazil, climate projections indicate an increase in average temperatures and the intensification of heatwaves across several regions, leading to a rise in air conditioning demand in both residential and commercial buildings (Triana et al., 2018; Invidiata & Ghisi, 2016). These variations in outdoor temperature directly influence the thermal load of buildings, thereby affecting energy efficiency and indoor thermal comfort (Diniz et al., 2017). In light of these projections, there is an urgent need to explore and implement strategies that can enhance the thermal response of buildings in the face of these changing conditions, with

a particular focus on social housing (SH), where access to air conditioning may be constrained (Triana et al., 2015).

Steel slag (SS) has been identified as a material with favorable thermal properties, particularly due to its high thermal inertia, which allows it to absorb and release heat gradually (Franco et al., 2019). In the field of construction, SS has been utilized as aggregate in concrete and mortar, contributing not only to the reduction of the environmental impact of conventional materials but also to the enhancement of the thermal performance of buildings (Chilukuri et al., 2023; Gonçalves et al., 2016). Furthermore, SS's capacity for adaptation to diverse climates positions it as a promising solution for enhancing building thermal efficiency under varied environmental conditions. However, for its long-term application as a bioclimatic strategy to be viable, it is essential to evaluate its thermal performance across multiple climatic scenarios and over time.

In consideration of Brazil's climatic diversity—ranging from hot and humid equatorial regions to subtropical zones with more pronounced winters (Brito Filho & Oliveira, 2014)—the thermal behavior of SS is expected to vary accordingly. To assess its effectiveness in different contexts, this study will be conducted in 9 Brazilian cities, selected based on their distinct climatic profiles.

Accordingly, the objective of this study is to evaluate the thermal performance of SS in SH, based on thermal load analysis and comfort indicators, considering various Brazilian climatic scenarios. The evaluation encompasses projections extending up to the year 2050, thereby exploring the strategy's adaptability to climate change as well as potential long-term challenges related to the durability and stability of the material. Contrary to earlier studies that examined the thermal performance of materials in isolation or under static climatic conditions, this research adopts an integrated and forward-looking approach. It assesses the application of SS in SH across multiple Brazilian climates, based on future climate change scenarios. This strategy is both innovative and aligned with principles of sustainable for climate-responsive building design.

2. Materials and methods

The study was based on real housing units built as part of the “*Vila Reciclos*” project, developed by the Federal University of Ouro Preto (UFOP). This project utilized masonry blocks containing steel slag (SS) as wall components. The buildings, which also feature green roofs and natural ventilation through stack effect and cross-ventilation, served as the basis for computer simulations aimed at evaluating the thermal performance of SS as a bioclimatic strategy. While the model incorporates additional passive solutions, the analysis is focused on the SS wall, with its specific contribution examined under various climatic scenarios.

2.1 Building description

The green roof consists of a layered structure designed to support plant growth while providing insulation and water management benefits. The layers include 5 cm of expanded clay for drainage, a geotextile mat to prevent soil erosion, 8 cm of substrate to support plant roots, and a 5 cm layer of peanut grass for vegetation cover.

The models accurately represented the actual geometry of the *Vila Reciclos* housing units, incorporating the thermophysical properties of materials (Table 1). Two scenarios were compared: one model featuring a slag masonry block (SS) and another reference model (REF) with traditional concrete masonry block, both subjected to the same boundary conditions. While the model incorporates additional passive strategies, such as green roofing and ventilation by stack effect, the analysis focuses on the thermal influence of the slag wall.

Table 1 – Thermophysical properties of the opaque materials in the real model

Properties		Mortars			Structural block	Concrete		Ceramic floor
		Floor	Slab	Wall		Floor	Slab	
Thickness [m]		0,04	0,02	0,005	0,14	0,15	0,10	0,01
Thermal conductivity [W/mK]		0,48	0,48	0,48	0,59	0,42	0,42	0,90
Density [kg/m ³]		2126	2126	2126	2723	2521	2521	1600
Specific heat [J/kgK]		1000	1000	1000	1000	1000	1000	920
Absorptivity	Thermal	0,90	0,90	*	0,90	0,90	0,90	0,90
	Solar	0,90	0,70	*	0,73	0,70	0,70	0,65
	Visible	0,90	0,70	*	0,73	0,70	0,70	0,65

* The absorptivity of the white walls is 0,11 and that of the gray walls is 0,70.

Source: Adapted from Franco et al. (2019), Baêta & Souza (1997).

In this article, from the four houses constructed as part of the study, SH 2 and 4 were selected as models of the two-bedroom typology due to their similarity in design and layout, ensuring consistency in the analysis.

Figure 1 – Highlight of the 2-bedroom typology analyzed: a) section and b) floor plan

2.2 Simulations, climatic scenarios and indicators

The validation of the model was conducted using environmental monitoring data that was collected on-site at the *Vila Reciclos* project. The calibration process was executed through a manual iterative method, which entailed the comparison of measured and simulated values of dry-bulb and operative temperatures. Statistical analysis was based on the Mean Bias Error (MBE), calculated on an hourly basis, with acceptable limits defined by ASHRAE Guideline 14 ($\pm 10\%$) (ASHRAE, 2002).

The simulations were performed using EnergyPlus software (version 24.2), in accordance with the criteria established by the Brazilian standard NBR 15575-1 (ABNT, 2024). To implement the stack effect in the model with natural ventilation, the high windows were set to remain open from 18:00 to 10:00 the following day

during summer and spring, and closed between 10:00 and 18:00, as well as throughout winter and autumn. A total of nine Brazilian cities were selected to represent the country's climatic diversity for the purposes of this study and their locations are displayed in Figure 2.

Thermal assessment of thermal performance was contingent upon two primary factors: the annual heating and cooling loads, and the percentage of hours falling within the range of thermal comfort. This evaluation was conducted within the confines of an operative temperature range between 18°C and 26°C, a range that remained consistent throughout the year.

Figure 2 – Geographic distribution of representative cities and their climatic profiles in Brazil

To assess the thermal resilience of SS in the face of climate change, projections were incorporated through the year 2050, based on the most pessimistic scenario based on Representative Concentration Pathways (RCP 8.5), and adjusted to reflect projected increases in average extreme temperatures (Table 2) (Climate.OneBuilding, 2024; Tomrukcu & Ashrafian, 2024).

Table 2 – Characteristics of representative cities

City (BZ/Climate type)	Level [m]	Annual mean temperature [°C]		Annual mean relative humidity [%]	
		Present	2050	Present	2050
Curitiba-PR (1M/Cfb)	934	17,48	19,36	84,39	81,80
Porto Alegre-RS (2R/Cfa)	3	20,11	21,63	79,81	79,73
Florianópolis-SC (3A/Cfa)	3	21,00	22,35	81,59	81,97
Belo Horizonte-MG (3B/Cwb)	334	21,29	23,76	69,75	62,51
Rio de Janeiro-RJ (4A/Am)	2	24,19	26,19	78,66	72,84
Goiânia-GO (4B/Am)	863	23,60	26,99	66,54	56,71
Natal-RN (5A/As)	30	26,10	28,16	80,59	75,67
Cuiabá-MT (5B/Aw)	176	26,09	29,71	73,80	59,82
Manaus-AM (6A/Af)	92	26,71	28,59	84,31	75,48

Source: Adapted from LABEEE (2004), Climate.Onebuilding (2024).

3. Results and analysis

3.1 Impact of temperature and humidity on thermal performance

Figure 3a shows that the highest annual thermal loads for the SS model occur in hot climates, such as Af (6A) and Aw (5B), where values exceed 1300 kWh/year. This behavior may be linked to high annual average temperatures (T °C), greater than 26 °C, combined with low daily thermal variation (Figure 3b), which limits passive cooling efficiency. SS, as a material with high thermal capacity, tends to absorb and retain heat (Franco et al., 2019), which can be an unfavorable factor in climates with predominance of constant heat (Almusaed et al., 2020). Rising temperatures inversely correlate with efficiency on tropical and humid subtropical with oceanic climates. Additionally, these climates exhibit high relative humidity levels, notably in Af (6A), which exceeds 84% (Figure 3c).

The high humidity levels, reduce natural ventilation efficacy and amplify perceived heat, particularly when paired with high temperatures (Kyritsi & Michael, 2020). In humid climates, performance variation is minimal (32%-49%), despite significant average temperature fluctuations (21-27° C). In contrast, dry climates like Cwb (3B), with an average relative humidity of 70%, demonstrate much lower thermal loads (24 kWh/year). This is attributed to milder average temperatures (~21 °C) and greater daily thermal amplitude (10 °C and 33 °C), with enhance passive cooling. Here, SS combined with natural ventilation acts as a more effective thermal regulator, leveraging these conditions (Hu et al., 2023). While average efficiency is higher in such scenarios, results vary widely (36%-79%) within the same mean temperature range.

Figure 3 – Annual thermal loads (a), temperature profiles (b), and relative humidity (c) for different climate zones using the SS model

3.2 Performance projection to 2050

Based on projections for 2050, there is a significant increase in annual thermal load in tropical climates (Figure 4a), particularly Aw (5B) and Af (6A), where the cooling load (CL) exceeds 4900 kWh/year, even with the application of the SS strategy. This trend is linked to rising maximum temperatures (Figure 4b), which reach up to 45 °C during the hottest periods of the year. Heating loads (HL) tend to disappear in tropical regions, persisting only in colder climates, like Cfb (1M), where sub-zero temperatures are still recorded. Additionally, relative humidity (RH) (Figure 4c) plays an important role in thermal comfort and the passive strategy performance. For example, in the Af (6A) climate (RH=75%), the SS strategy achieves a percentage of hours on operative temperature range (PHOTR) of 58% in 2050, lower than the current 86%. This highlights the critical impact of combined heat and humidity, which compromises the efficacy of passive cooling mechanisms such as natural ventilation (Ahmed et al., 2021; Bay et al., 2022). Despite these challenges, the results suggest that the SS strategy still mitigates part of the total projected thermal load for 2050, particularly in intermediate climates. This reinforces its potential as an adaptative solution in the face of climate change (Hu et al., 2023).

Figure 4 – Projected thermal loads (a), maximum temperature profiles (b), and relative humidity (c) for 2050 in different climate zones using the SS model

3.3 Comparison between thermal loads in REF and SS

Figure 5 presents a comparison between the monthly heating thermal loads in the REF and SS models, both under current climate conditions and in a pessimistic future climate change scenario (year 2050 — RPC 8.5). In general, a reduction in projected heating loads for 2050 is observed compared to the current climate, at least 59%, which aligns with the predicted increase in average temperatures, highlighting the importance of considering future demands in the development of sustainable projects. Additionally, in all analyzed climates, the model incorporating SS as a building material shows lower heating demands compared to the REF model.

This result highlights the potential of SS as a bioclimatic strategy, favored by its high thermal inertia, contributing to greater stability of internal temperatures (Jeong et al., 2023). The difference between REF and SS is particularly notable in colder climates, such as humid subtropical zone oceanic climate Cfb (1M) and Cfa (2R), where SS contributes to the thermal load reductions exceeding 21%. In mixed and humid climates, like humid subtropical Cfa (3A), the thermal load reduction was more pronounced, around 33%. On the other hand, in hot tropical climates, such as Am, Aw, As, and Af, the heating loads are negligible, and the effect of the strategies is residual. These findings reinforce the relevance of using alternative materials like SS in cold climates, where its thermal effect is more significant, even in the face of future climate scenarios (Madhusudanan & Nallusamy, 2022).

Figure 5 – Comparison of heating load between present and forecast for 2050 (RPC 8.5)

Figure 6 presents a comparison of monthly cooling loads under both current conditions and the 2050 projection. In contrast to the observed behavior of heating loads, there is a discernible increase in projected cooling loads for the year 2050, particularly in tropical and subtropical climates such as Am (4A), Cwa (4B), As (5A), Aw (5B), and Af (6A). This increase is directly related to global warming, which intensifies the need for passive and/or mechanical cooling strategies in indoor environments (Khourchid et al., 2022).

In comparative terms, the SS model exhibited a marginal superiority over the REF model across all climates, with reductions ranging from 32% to 100% in the present, achieving thermal load reductions of up to 85 kWh per month. This behavior indicates that SS can also contribute to mitigating thermal gains in hot climates, although its impact is less pronounced compared to heating scenarios. The greatest efficiency gains were observed in dry tropical climates, like Am (4B) and Aw (5B), where the difference between REF and SS exceeds the 130 kWh/month in 2050, leading to demand reductions of between 22% and 53% in the future. These results demonstrate that SS, in addition to its positive effect on thermal comfort in cold regions, can also play an important role in mitigating thermal loads under scenarios of intense warming (Castro et al., 2020).

Figure 6 – Comparison of cooling load between present and forecast for 2050 (RPC 8.5)

3.4 Thermal comfort: within the comfort zone

Figure 7 illustrates the percentage of time during which indoor operative temperatures remained within the thermal comfort zone (PHOTR), both for the current scenario and the 2050 projection, with and without the SS strategy. Generally, SS increased PHOTR in all cities, with a notable increase of 8% in the tropical zone without dry season — Af (6A) — which is particularly significant given that this climate has the lowest PHOTR. Additionally, milder climates, such as Cfb (1M) and Cfa (2R e 3A), exhibit the best thermal comfort performance, with percentages exceeding 8% in the present. For these climates, the difference between the REF and SS models is relatively small, but still favorable to using the SS strategy, demonstrating that passive solutions can maintain or even improve the thermal performance without increasing energy consumption (Elaouzy & El Fadar, 2022b). In the future (RPC 8.5), however, there is a general trend of reduced PHOTR in nearly all analyzed climates, with more pronounced declines in hot and humid climates, such as Am (4A), Aw (4B), and Af (6A). In hot climates generally — Am (4A), Aw (4B e 5B), As (5A), and Af (6A) — the use of SS partially mitigates the negative impacts, as even with SS, PHOTR does not exceed 75%. This reassures the importance of integrating passive strategies into building planning, especially in regions vulnerable to climate change (Liu et al., 2020).

Figure 7 – Present and projected thermal comfort performance (PHOTR) with and without the SS strategy

4. Conclusions

This study evaluated the applicability of steel slag (SS) as a bioclimatic strategy for social housing in across different regions of Brazil. Though simulations conducted in nine representative Brazilian cities spanning diverse climatic zones, the thermal performance of SS was analyzed under current and future climatic conditions, with projections extending to 2050 under the most pessimistic scenario (RCP 8.5).

The results indicate that the use of SS in walls provides significant improvements in building thermal performance. A comparative analysis between the reference model (conventional blocks) and the SS model demonstrated substantial reductions in heating and cooling thermal loads, alongside enhanced thermal comfort across all evaluated climatic zones.

In humid subtropical zone oceanic climates, such as Cfb (1M) and Cfa (2M), SS reduced heating demands by up to 22%, while in humid subtropical zone with dry winter, like Cwb (3B), cooling loads decreased by 79%, confirming its efficacy as a high thermal inertia material. In tropical regions without dry season, such as Af (6A), SS exhibited partial resilience, increasing the PHOTR by 8%, even under high humidity. However, in future scenarios (2050), its performance will face challenges due to rising temperatures and climatic extremes. In critical zones, like the tropical zone with dry season climate — Aw (5B) — where projected maximum temperatures will reach 45 °C, SS still mitigates 22% of thermal loads, but thermal comfort will drop to 41%, underscoring the need for complementary design adjustments.

Beyond reducing energy demands, SS contributed for the maintaining thermal comfort, even under severe climatic projections. The material demonstrated potential to mitigate the effects of extreme temperatures and high humidity, reinforcing its viability as a passive solution for social housing, particularly in humid tropical zones, where its bioclimatic potential is maximized. Conversely, while effective in tropical climates, project adaptations — such as optimizing integration with natural ventilation and green roofs — are recommended to further reduce energy demand.

In conclusion, steel slag represents a sustainable and effective alternative for adapting buildings to future climates. Its applications in different Brazilian climate zones highlights its versatility and robustness as a complementary strategy for enhancing thermal performance and energy efficiency in the housing sector.

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